

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

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WP2 – Outcome Driven Healthcare

D2.2 ICHOM Standards Defined Using OMOP Terminology

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.
ICHOM	ICHOM (International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement, www.ichom.org) is a not-for-profit organization founded in 2012 that aims to unlock the potential of value-based healthcare by defining global Standard Sets of outcome measures and driving adoption and reporting of these measures worldwide.

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Standard Set	An ICHOM Standard Set encompasses standardized outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition. ICHOM standard sets are developed through consensus and the process involves experts and patient representatives, to ensure the standard sets include those outcomes most relevant to patients. Currently, 28 standard sets are available.
PROM – Patient Report Outcome measure	Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) are instruments, usually questionnaires, measuring the patients’ views of their health status.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

WP2 will review and provide recommendations to enable the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) - Common Data Model (CDM) and vocabularies to include International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement (ICHOM) standard sets. A standard set encompasses standardised outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition. Currently, 28 standard sets are available (www.ichom.org).

For the prioritized ICHOM standard sets (inflammatory arthritis and prostate cancer) identified in D2.1, this deliverable describes the extent of coverage of the OMOP-CDM with respect to the ICHOM standards. Our preliminary analysis has shown approximate 70% and 50% coverage of the inflammatory arthritis and prostate cancer sets respectively. Furthermore, issues that need to be addressed and recommendations both for the OMOP-CDM and ICHOM on how to implement these are identified. In subsequent deliverables, these recommendations will be tested to determine best approaches. The results of these proof of concepts will then be used to specify adaptations and approaches that will be helpful in supporting the Outcome Driven Healthcare use case across the majority of conditions representing the global disease burden.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of WP2 is to enable the transition towards outcomes-driven healthcare systems in Europe. This can be achieved by enhancing the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) framework so that it can be used in the context of regulatory approval, health technology assessment (HTA), and for payer purposes. As the EHDEN project is using the OMOP-CDM to build a federated network of data sources standardized to a common data model, WP2 will test if and how the OMOP-CDM can be used for regulatory, HTA and payer activities.

ICHOM is a not-for-profit organization founded in 2012 that aims to unlock the potential of value-based healthcare by defining global Standard Sets of outcome measures and driving adoption and reporting of these measures worldwide. As standard sets of measures are collected in clinical practice, transparency and benchmarking of outcomes achieved facilitates rapid learning to improve care and drive efficient use of health care resources and treatments.

A standard set encompasses standardized outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition. ICHOM standard sets are developed through consensus and the process involves experts and patient representatives, to ensure the standard sets include those outcomes most relevant to patients. Currently, 28 standard sets are available (www.ichom.org).

The two priority disease areas selected by EHDEN D2.1 are inflammatory arthritis and prostate cancer. These ICHOM standards will be enabled within OMOP-CDM first and will be used as testcases for the development of the relevant dashboards planned under D2.4 and D2.5 (for M24). As such, these priority disease areas will showcase how the ICHOM use case is to be supported by OMOP-CDM and the EHDEN/OHDSI platform.

This deliverable (D2.2) provides insight on how ICHOM standard sets can be implemented using the OMOP-CDM. This deliverable describes how the ICHOM standard sets as prioritized in D2.1 are captured in current OMOP-CDM concepts. It identifies gaps in OMOP-CDM as well as issues that will need to be taken into consideration when defining ICHOM standard sets in OMOP terminology. Further, the present document discusses recommendations on how to solve typical and/or structural issues that may arise. In subsequent deliverables, these recommendations will be tested to determine which approach and/or alternatives will best solve issues identified.

2. METHODS

The present deliverable D2.2 aims at describing how the data elements in ICHOM standard sets can or should be defined using OMOP terminology. The steps undertaken to assess this include: 1) Examining current coverage of OMOP-CDM to ICHOM standards, 2) Identifying gaps and issues with mapping to OMOP vocabularies, 3) Describing structural aspects of standard sets and requirements of the ICHOM use case (benchmarking and improvement of quality of care) and 4) Proposing an approach to support ICHOM standard sets in OMOP-CDM.

- 1. Examination of current coverage of OMOP-CDM to ICHOM Standards:** Athena (<http://athena.ohdsi.org>), a browser tool containing standardized vocabularies for all CDM domains, was used to conduct explorative concept mapping, identifying possible matches between items in the ICHOM sets and corresponding concepts in OMOP Standard vocabularies.

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2. Identification of gaps and issues in mapping to OMOP vocabularies:

The above exercise leaves some items without corresponding OMOP concepts. This concerns both specific and general gaps, i.e., domains or categories of data that currently are not appropriately defined in OMOP-CDM (such as patient reported outcome questionnaires). Potential issues were also identified when ICHOM items matched with more than one possible alternative standard concept in OMOP.

3. Description of structural aspects of standard sets and requirements of the ICHOM use case:

In addition to risk adjustment variables and outcomes specified, there are additional data elements contained in an ICHOM standard set that are relevant for implementation purposes. We described the typical structure of standard sets (eg. inclusion and exclusion criteria, time points for data collection), typical 'data formats', possible semantic ambiguities, mandatory and conditional data elements.

4. Proposal for an approach toward supporting ICHOM standard sets in OMOP-CDM

Issues identified in the previous steps were summarized and discussed with a view to propose a workable approach to support the Outcome Driven Healthcare use case.

One component focuses on issues related to (structural) gaps in OMOP vocabularies and potential conceptual ambiguities that need to be reviewed by OMOP vocabulary experts. For other issues, this deliverable proposes an approach that needs to be implemented and tested in subsequent deliverables. Examples in point are the definition of ICHOM inclusion/exclusion criteria in OMOP terminology and the way ICHOM benchmarking metrics are best implemented – possibly by using re-useable phenotypes or scripts that can capture the business logic of ICHOM standard sets. Identification and prioritization of issues that need to be addressed in subsequent steps, will be discussed specifically in deliverable D2.3.

3. RESULTS

A standard set encompasses information on the inclusion criteria for a given condition (definition of the condition the standard is applicable to), a set of outcomes that are considered most important (including patient reported outcomes measures), measurement tools to detect these changes, treatment approaches covered, and time points for assessment and risk adjustment factors so that outcomes measured are meaningfully comparable.

3.1 Current coverage of ICHOM standard sets in OMOP-CDM

Using Athena, explorative concept mapping was conducted, identifying possible matches between items in the ICHOM sets and corresponding concepts in OMOP standard vocabularies.

For **Inflammatory Arthritis**, 70% of the terms are covered in OMOP-CDM.

Of the 52 items in this Standard Set,

- 24 items could directly be matched to corresponding concepts in OMOP-CDM
- 14 items could be matched partially, with open questions or with more than one candidate concept; to be discussed
- 7 items could not be matched directly to a (standard) concept in the vocabulary table. This concerns a question about the disease activity target being reached, and 6 questions from the Work Productivity Activity Index (WPAI) PROM questionnaire.

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- 7 items are auxiliary variables, asking about which PROM, questionnaire or composite score are used to measure subsequent variables, or about the unit being used for a particular numerical variable.

In our analysis (see Annex 1), most of the items in the standard set were matched to Conditions (particularly: comorbidity data) and Observations. The items that have more than one possible match can often be modelled as Observations and/or Measurements – e.g., questionnaires for patient-reported measurement of pain, fatigue and activity limitations. Incidentally, OMOP concepts in the Procedure or Drug domain are relevant – for example, the ‘high blood pressure’ comorbidity, which is defined as “patient has hypertension and/or uses antihypertensive medication”.

For **(localized and/or advanced) prostate cancer**, 50% of the terms are covered in OMOP-CDM.

Of the 265 items in the two Prostate Cancer sets (122 items for localized prostate cancer; 153 items for advanced prostate cancer, respectively):

- 70 items can directly be matched to corresponding concepts in OMOP-CDM
- 120 items could be matched partially, with open questions or with more than one candidate concept; to be discussed.
- 75 items could not be matched directly to a (standard) concept in the vocabulary table.
- 60 of these items concern questions from two PROMs, i.e., the EPIC26 Quality of Life questionnaire and the LIBID Utilization of Sexual Medications/Devices questionnaire. These PROMs are used in both standard sets.

These standard sets overlap each other but are not the same. Compared to the inflammatory arthritis set, the prostate cancer sets include more clinical variables, with the majority of these being partially matched variables. Many of the variables correspond to either Measurements and/or Observations in OMOP. Like in the inflammatory arthritis set, these standard sets also contain some disease-specific observations and treatment variables that require further attention. Different from the inflammatory arthritis set, the prostate cancer sets contain quite a few items on treatment modalities, asking for start- and stopdate and other timing attributes. These will require more elaborate, composite concept mapping. Finally, several variables in these two sets have free-text response options.

3.2 Gaps and issues in mapping OMOP (standard) vocabularies

In the concept mapping exercise, not all items in the ICHOM Standard Sets to corresponding OMOP concepts resulting in gaps in OMOP-ICHOM coverage. These gaps relate to general areas currently not covered in OMOP-CDM as well as disease- or treatment specific concepts that were not available in the vocabulary table / Athena browser.

3.2.1 General gaps: PROMs - Patient Reported Outcome questionnaires

Inflammatory Arthritis:

- Most patient reported outcome items have at least one matching PROMs concept in OMOP-CDM.
- Not all PROMs listed in the Standard Set are supported. For some items (e.g. Fatigue) the general adult questionnaire(s) are supported while the pediatric counterpart (PedsQL4.0 Fatigue Total Score) is not.
- Most of the inflammatory arthritis PROMs are available in the OMOP-CDM vocabulary table because they are supported by the Snomed CT standard

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vocabulary. One PROM, the Work productivity activity index (WPAI), is not supported in Snomed CT. Hence, it not supported by OMOP-CDM.

Prostate Cancer:

- The prostate cancer sets define only one PROM questionnaire per patient reported outcome. The Advanced Prostate Cancer set uses one PROM questionnaire that is supported – the EORTCQLQC. That is, this PROM is included as an assessment-scale concept in Snomed CT. The underlying questions do not seem to be available in OMOP-CDM.
- Two other questionnaires, the EPIC26 Quality of Life questionnaire and the LIBID Utilization of Sexual Medications/Devices, are used in both Prostate Cancer sets but not supported in OMOP-CDM.

In this analysis, we restricted matching ICHOM items to concepts supported in OMOP-CDM version 5.3, the version supported by the tools in the EHDEN/OHDSI platform. Future work will identify whether and how it is possible to model the PROMs with the Survey table in OMOP-CDM v6.x.

3.2.2 Specific gaps – missing specific standard concepts:

The items in the prioritized standard sets that lack a matching concept in the vocabulary table are mostly Treatment Factors and/or Complications of Treatment. The following are reasons why a proper match cannot be made for these items:

1. The ICHOM definition does not align with concepts that are supported in OMOP-CDM. This can concern the definition itself ('Patient has suffered from a serious adverse event *in the last 12 months*') and/or the response options specified (e.g. SAE-Type: the response options in the standard set do not readily align with similar concepts in OMOP vocabulary table).
2. The disease- or treatment specific concept in the standard set may be not available at all in the standard vocabularies (e.g., arthritis disease activity and disease activity target, prostate cancer disease progress measures, treatment specific parameters).
3. The ICHOM variable may specifically define a patient-reported item, while the closest matching concept in OMOP refers to a clinically reported data item.

3.2.3 Potentially ambiguous concept mappings:

There were instances found in the ICHOM standard sets that yielded potentially ambiguous concept mappings. These examples are in need of further review and discussion, either because they seem to match with more than one possible alternative concept in OMOP, or because the items in the Standard Sets may focus on specific attributes or aspects (date, dose, intent, target evaluation). Representative examples from the prioritized Standard Sets are described below.

Comorbidities

- Comorbidities can be primarily modeled as Condition and/or as Observation. The inflammatory arthritis set lists the comorbidities in distinct variables, and the prostate cancer sets uses one item, referring to a Self-Administered Comorbidity Questionnaire.
- Difficulties in developing a consistent approach to model concepts such as 'Other heart diseases' (i.e., other than those included in other response options)

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- Malignancies/Other cancer (within last x years) lack specificity
- Leg Pain when walking due to poor circulation are composite concepts that needs further elaboration
- High blood pressure - this comorbidity can be defined in terms of an observation/condition but also in terms of drug utilization and/or procedures in present or past)

Treatment variables

- Timing aspects
 - Variables like ‘treatment *during last year*’ etc. will require composite concepts or Snomed attributes to capture in full.
 - Items asking for the Start and Stop date/year of a specific treatment modality can be modelled using composite concepts/relevant fields in the OMOP Procedure table, but also using Snomed attributes.
 - Ongoing treatments – to be re-modeled for observational data sets
- Other aspects/attributes of treatment
 - Therapy intent
 - Dose, nerve sparing status, etc.
 - Primary and secondary treatments
 - Disease/Standard set specific treatment modalities – including, for example: ‘active surveillance’, ‘watchful waiting’ resp. ‘active surveillance (watchful waiting)’.
 - Free text response options – it is not clear to which extent these are used and relevant in practice.

Complications

- Attributes specially asked for in standard sets will need to be modeled as composite concepts (e.g., complications due to a specific cause or in particular circumstances)
- Timing aspects and other attributes of complications will need to be captured in relation to a specific diagnosis or treatment event captured in another variable – this may require a generic approach to capture links and logical relations between different items in a standard set.

For the next phase of this work (D2.3), all items and matches proposed in the Annexes will be reviewed and discussed with vocabulary team experts in order to ensure that the adopted concept mapping approach aligns with current convention and modeling/mapping rules applied by the OHDSI vocabulary team.

3.3 Structural aspects of Standard Sets

We examined the structural aspects of the prioritised standard sets. After a high-level review of 28 standard sets, it is our view that these sets are representative of other ICHOM sets as they represent both chronic and acute conditions, contain the same structure and underlying logic, and comprehensively cover the data types included in a typical ICHOM standard set.

1. General layout of the Standard Sets

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The prioritized standard sets show typical variations that may occur. However, the general structure of ICHOM standard sets is consistent with the Category of each variable (left-most column in the data dictionary) ranging from Patient or Demographics, Baseline Factors and Tumor Factors to Treatment Factors and Complications and Health Status. Each item in the set has a Timing attribute with values like Baseline, Before/after surgery, 3 Month, 6 Month, and/or Annually. Further, there is a column indicating whether the listed item should be Clinician-reported or Patient-reported – this attribute can also have the value ‘Administrative’.

Variations may concern timing and reporting source attributes: these can vary between standard sets for the same concepts. For instance, comorbidities are patient-reported in the prostate cancer sets and clinician-reported in the inflammatory arthritis set.

It is not clear what the implications are in terms of eligibility of data sets for outcome benchmarking if specific data elements do not comply with these attributes and/or these attributes are unknown for OMOP version of data sets. One potential use for this information is to assess data appropriateness or quality

2. Criteria for inclusion and exclusion of patients

Coverage of the set is specified in the reference guides accompanying the standard sets. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are primarily defined in terms of the diagnosis and/or treatment modality of the patient. It is recommended to design a generic approach to capture those criteria in OMOP. A starting point for this approach may well be the OMOP/OHDSI cohort definitions and cohort pathways.

3. Typical ‘data formats’

The ICHOM standard sets contain data items that are typically defined as if they are collected prospectively. Currently, data formats and response options in the standard sets do not always align with observational data. ICHOM has initiated an exercise to ensure and improve the internal consistency (harmonization) of all standard sets. The suggestion here is to support and strengthen that initiative with recommendations based on OMOP experience with observational data sets.

4. Mandatory and conditional data elements

It is not clear if standard sets have items that are mandatory and if there are minimum requirements for specific outcome measures and/or benchmarking metrics. It will be important to develop business rules, if relevant, in a generic manner. One possible approach would be to make use of concept sets, cohort definitions, cohort pathways to define such logic in OMOP terminology. As an example, complex items can be defined extensively using Concept Sets, while conditional data items can be captured using cohort pathways. Timing rules for recurring data elements may also be captured using OMOP Cohort Pathways.

5. Typical ICHOM benchmarking metrics

Dashboard metrics & rules for benchmarking – e.g. for Prostate Cancer also need to be defined in OMOP terminology. The next deliverable will explore and try out how such metrics can be specified in phenotypes. Typical metrics would involve:

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- Outcomes of interest (both clinical and patient reported aspects of condition; health status)
- Length of treatment and type of intervention
- Baselines status and status after intervention
- Patient risk factors

For the next deliverable(s), structural aspects listed will be taken into consideration on a generic level, so that the approach adopted for these prioritized sets will eventually be applicable to all ICHOM Standard Sets.

3.4 An approach toward supporting ICHOM Standard Sets in OMOP

The present deliverable is focused on exploring how to define data items that are included in ICHOM Standard Sets in OMOP terminology, or rather, as standard concepts currently supported in OMOP-CDM. However, 100% coverage with matching concepts in the vocabulary table is not enough to support an ICHOM standard set. As the previous section indicates, the business rules and logic underlying a Standard Set need to be taken into consideration as well. Both the logical and physical data models need to be extended along with the vocabularies used to define the data.

Hence, we propose a twofold approach for the next steps in WP2, workstream Outcome Driven Healthcare:

1. Review and work out the suggested concept mappings for data items in the prioritized standard sets, establishing mappings of the data items in the ICHOM standard sets onto OMOP standard concepts in a manner that aligns with current convention and best practices of the OHDSI vocabulary team.
2. Explore and establish good practices for supporting the ICHOM use case by trying out the translated OMOP data items in combination with concept sets, cohort definitions, cohort pathways and other phenotypes designed to capture the business logic underlying ICHOM standard sets in a generic, re-useable manner.

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4. DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY OF RESULTS

4.1 Top line results

The prioritized ICHOM standard sets have reasonable coverage in OMOP. Based on our preliminary analysis, we can conclude that many of the items in ICHOM standard sets can be defined in OMOP-CDM. This needs to be further investigated and formally tested in the next deliverable (D2.3). In the present deliverable, we have explored and gathered issues and considerations which will specify which extensions are required to support ICHOM Standard Sets in OMOP-CDM.

1. Recommendation: the proposed concept mappings and suggestions made in this deliverable should be tested series of small proofs of concept. Specially for the following three issues, the suggested approaches should be Q`W25detailed in the next deliverable, D2.3:
 - **PROMs:** there are two alternative approaches to better support these instruments as they are used in ICHOM standard sets
 - a) OMOP-CDM can add to current coverage, which is mostly via the Snomed CT standard vocabulary. Hence, a possible approach is that either ICHOM and/or OHDSI can urge Snomed to support the PROM instruments that are used in ICHOM standard sets to fill in the gaps.
 - b) Even if Snomed CT would cover all ICHOM PROMs, there are countries in Europe that do not participate in Snomed. Hence, at least one proof of concept should be conducted to try out how and to what extent the Survey table/concepts added to OMOP v6.x would suffice to support ICHOM PROMs and other similar questionnaires.
 - **Treatment attributes:** a number of items in the ICHOM Standard Sets ask for specific attributes or aspects of treatments. There seem to be two ways to capture these in OMOP-CDM.
 - a) Make use of procedure attributes in Snomed CT
 - b) Elucidate composite concepts in OMOP-CDM to capture such items. This may be particularly relevant for timing attributes, as it will be possible to capture these using fields in the OMOP Procedure table.
 - **ICHOM business logic:** Business logic underlying ICHOM standard sets can be captured in phenotypes supported by OHDSI. like:
 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria – Cohort definitions
 2. More complex items (e.g., hypertension comorbidity) – Concept sets
 3. Conditional data elements, recurring subsets – Cohort pathways
 4. Benchmarking metrics – analytic phenotypes, R scripts?

This approach needs to be tested – is this feasible, how scalable is it, which requirements for the ICHOM standard sets would emerge from this approach?

2. **Harmonization of data elements, especially comorbidities and complications** - Data elements concerning comorbidities, complications and the like tend to vary substantially in terms of data format and/or structure in different ICHOM sets. This easily results in ambiguities.

During the subsequent phase of work, recommendations on harmonized definitions will emerge.

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4.2 Context of changes to ICHOM sets

1. There is currently an effort underway to harmonize data elements across standard sets. This involves retrospectively assessing instances of similar variables across sets (e.g. blood pressure, education level, BMI) and selecting one definition to be used. ICHOM plans on creating a term bank of these harmonized definition for use in Standard Sets by Q3 2020. The terms selected will be based on coverage in existing data standards and retention of semantics per the original standard set
2. Currently, standard sets list multiple PROMS for one topic/item. However, one of these usually is the preferred option or instrument of choice. ICHOM plans to make mappings between instruments available, in order to facilitate benchmarking and comparison of results across sites using recommended tools.
3. Harmonization of ICHOM ‘business logic’ underlying the standard sets is important in two ways:
 - Completeness of the collected data according to the Standard Set – which most likely is defined as a prospective data collection.
 - Conditional data items and/or instruments choices (e.g., adults versus pediatric questionnaires) - could be solvable with cohort pathway phenotypes, but it is not clear if the prioritized Standard Sets are representative in this regard.

4.3 Strengths / Limitations

This exercise was a first step at characterising ICHOM Standard Sets in context of OMOP-CDM. Proposed concept mappings are preliminary and will need to be reviewed by vocabulary team experts to ensure semantic interoperability between ICHOM standard set and OMOP-CDM

Nonetheless, the current findings are a good indication of issues that we can expect. The recommendation to test the proposed approaches and solutions is meant to ensure that we able to test this approach in practice. The subsequent deliverable will include a few smaller, partial proofs of concepts.

4.4 Implications for all ICHOM sets

The considerations described here have implications for changes and scalability of process to all ICHOM sets (and extension to D2.3 & the dashboard in D2.4/D 2.5) as well as for the eventual goals of supporting the ICHOM benchmarking use case in a federated network of data sources standardized to OMOP-CDM. To make most efficient use of data for benchmarking purposes, it is important that standardized information is being collected.

Furthermore, dashboards visualizing these data may be used for feedback on individual patient-level resp. for hospital- or practitioner-level insights. Such dashboard may be used to: 1) Improve direct clinical care, 2) facilitate comparisons and transparency on outcomes patients can expect, and 3) generate systems-level use of data (reimbursement, audit & research purposes):

5. CONCLUSION

The present deliverable represents a first step towards defining ICHOM Standard Sets in terms of OMOP-CDM. We have explored how to define the Standard Sets prioritized in D2.1. Based on the

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results of this exercise, we expect that it will be possible to support ICHOM Standard Sets in OMOP. Moreover, in our view, it should be possible to develop a generic approach and establish good practices for supporting the ICHOM Outcome Driven Healthcare use case in OMOP on the basis of the prioritized standard sets.

5.1 Recommendations for next steps

For the next steps, we envision the following:

1. Review of proposed mappings and suggested approaches to ensure and improve semantic interoperability between OMOP and ICHOM
2. Discussion of remodeling decisions and recommendations made to facilitate vocabulary mapping
3. Define generic approaches for concept mapping
4. Describe ICHOM benchmarking metrics in a formal vocabulary to aid collection and reporting. Both the logical and physical data models need to be extended along with the vocabularies used to define the data. In OMOP terminology, this can be done using concept sets, cohort definitions, cohort pathways and other phenotypes.
5. Testing the above in small-scale proofs of concept to establish robust good/best practices for supporting the Outcome Driven Healthcare use case.

	D2.2 – ICHOM Standards Defined Using OMOP Terminology		
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ANNEXES

Annex 1

- 1 a) spreadsheet for Inflammatory Arthritis
- 1 b) spreadsheet for localized Prostate Cancer
- 1 c) spreadsheet for advanced Prostate Cancer